

Collection of patients with glioblastoma multiforme confirmed by biopsy and MR

ID: 40dbe9fb-c607-445d-a582-dea531b676b1

URL: <https://eucaim-node.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/40dbe9fb-c607-445d-a582-dea531b676b1/details>

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Studies count: 198

Subjects count: 50

Age range: Between 25 years and 78 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): HEAD, BRAIN, Unknown

Modality: MR